

FLEXURAL BEHAVIOR OF CARBON/GLASS AND BASALT TEXTILE REINFORCED CONCRETE (TRC) I-BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

Textile-reinforced concrete and mortar (referred to as TRC, TRM or FRCM in the literature) are composite materials that can be used to fabricate lightweight elements and structural concrete with complex geometries in minimal thicknesses. In this paper, two different types of composites were developed by using bidirectional textiles composed of basalt (BFRP) or carbon/glass (CFRP/GFRP) fibres and a varying number of reinforcement materials (one to three layers). Later, the composite materials were applied on TRC I-beams and their load-carrying behaviour subjected to bending moments is presented.

KEYWORDS

Textile Reinforced Concrete (TRC); I-section beam; Carbon/glass textile; Basalt textile; Bending.

INTRODUCTION

Steel is the most used reinforcing material in concrete due to its ductile behaviour and high tensile strength. However, its use shows disadvantages since it requires an adequate concrete cover for corrosion protection, leading to the use of larger sections, and presents high carbon emissions during production (Lior *et al.*, 2020; Venigalla *et al.*, 2022).

In the context of replacing conventional steel reinforcement with FRP materials, Inman *et al.* (2017) compared the mechanical and environmental performance of using internal reinforcement composed of basalt fibre-reinforced polymer (BFRP) against steel in precast elements. It was concluded that precast BFRP concrete beams have approximately half the emissions of steel-reinforced concrete beams.

Garg and Shrivastava (2019) analytically compared the environmental and economic viability of different FRP reinforcements as a substitute for traditional steel in RC beams. The results show that basalt reinforcement presents a much-reduced environmental intensity per strength unit. Furthermore, it was stated that BFRP, CFRP, and GFRP-reinforced beams used less energy and produced fewer CO₂ emissions than conventional steel-reinforced beams. This is because FRP-reinforced beams perform better than steel-reinforced beams due to the lightweight and high tensile strength of the composite materials. As a result, FRP materials may play an essential part in the construction industry's attempts to reduce its environmental footprint and hence in the worldwide sustainable act.

Thus, possible substitutions of steel as reinforcement have been globally explored and the use of Textile-Reinforced Concrete (TRC), or Textile-Reinforced Mortar (TRM), was proposed, replacing the conventional reinforcement with textiles.

The TRC is a composite material of high-performance fine-grained concrete and textiles. At the same time, the TRM combines high-strength fibres in the form of textiles with inorganic matrices, such as cement hydraulic-lime-based mortars. Both materials are low-cost, friendly for manual workers, fire-resistant, compatible with concrete and masonry substrate materials, applied on wet surfaces or at low temperatures, and exhibit good tensile strength, ductility, energy absorption capacity and load-carrying capacity. Also, they can reduce energy consumption, carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, and they can be used to produce structures with modular and complex shapes while eliminating the risk of corrosion (Lior *et al.*, 2020). For all these reasons, TRC or TRM is progressively becoming more attractive (Cascardi *et al.*, 2017; Leone *et al.*, 2017; Kariou *et al.*, 2018).

Textile mesh materials used as the TRM/TRC composite reinforcement consist of fibre strands arranged in two or more directions, with an open-mesh configuration, to increase the mechanical interlock between the mesh and the matrix. Figure 1 shows textiles that can be used as reinforcement in TRC or TRM systems, while Figure 2 presents the average behaviour of some FRP fibres.

Figure 1: Textile fibre reinforcements: (a) carbon fibre textile; (b) glass fibre textile; (c) basalt fibre textile; (d) polyphenylene bezobisoxazole fibre textile (PBO) and (e) steel fibre textile (Koutas *et al.*, 2018)

Figure 2: Relationship between tensile stress versus strain for some of the FRP fibres (FIB Bulletin 90, 2019)

The composition of the concrete or the mortar used as a matrix significantly affects the response as a composite material (Figure 3). The impregnation of fibres with the cementitious matrix is essential for a good bond between the fibres and the matrix. This material must include fine granules and should have a plastic consistency, good workability, low viscosity, and sufficient shear strength (to prevent the debonding of the composite material from the substrate); hence, cement-based materials are widely used as matrices.

Figure 3: Composite material

Besides its uses for repairing, retrofitting, and rehabilitating existing concrete and masonry, TRC/TRM can potentially build thin, modular, low-weight structures and slender concrete members. Thus, this composite material can be used for new constructions and load-bearing structural members, as well as precast elements (Scholzen *et al.*, 2015a), shell structures (Scholzen *et al.*, 2015b; Sharei *et al.*, 2017), parking slabs (Schumann *et al.*, 2018), and sandwich elements (Colombo *et al.*, 2015).

I-section beams with textile-reinforced concrete

Goliath *et al.* (2021) evaluated the flexural behaviour of carbon textile-reinforced concrete (TRC) I-beams. Thus, three 2000 mm long beams having I-sections with 80 mm of flange width, 180 mm of depth and 12.5 mm of thickness for both web and flange were fabricated.

A flexible carbon textile coated with styrene-butadiene rubber (SBR) resin was used in the study. It was a bidirectional mesh with 8.5 and 10 mm openings and 4.2 and 2.7 mm widths in the warp and weft directions, respectively. This material presented a tensile strength of 1140 MPa and an average modulus of elasticity of 189 GPa. To improve the bond between the textile and the cementitious matrix, an extra impregnation with epoxy resin and sand – referred to as rigid impregnation – was applied over the yarns. Thus, Sikadur32 and natural sand had the same grain size as the sand used as fine aggregate in the matrix (1.18 mm) was used. Also, this study used two different types of matrices: the plain concrete and the strain-hardening cement-based composite (SHCC) with 2% in volume of PVA (Polyvinyl Alcohol) microfibers, designated M1 and M2, respectively.

The beams were tested in a four-point bending configuration over an 1800 mm span and with a shear span of 750 mm. A hinge was placed over the load distribution beam to ensure equal forces were applied at the loading points. Testing was conducted using a servo-controlled hydraulic actuator with a load capacity of 500 kN under displacement control at a 1 mm/min rate. Figure 4 presents some details of the reinforcement and the test layout used in the experimental program.

Figure 4: (a) reinforcement, (b) casting and (c) overview of test setup (dimensions in mm).
Goliath *et al.* (2021)

According to the authors, the beam with plain matrix and reference textile exhibited premature shear failure due to the web-flange junction's poor ability to transfer shear forces. The extra impregnation of the textile and the use of the SHCC matrix improved the junction behaviour and changed the failure mode from shear to flexure.

In this context, the experimental program herein proposed and held at the University of Birmingham/UK included the development of the TRC composites and the investigation of the flexural behaviour of TRC I-beams with two different textiles (CFRP/GFRP and BFRP) and three different reinforcement ratios (one to three layers).

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Materials and mechanical characterization

Cementitious matrix

A premixed blend of dried sand, fine aggregate, cement, and additives was used in the experimental program. According to the manufacturer, this material presents a compressive strength of C32/40, with a mixing ratio between 2.0 to 2.8 l and w/c ranging from 0.1 to 0.14 (for a 20 kg bag). The specimens and beams herein analyzed presented a w/c of 0.1.

To evaluate the mechanical properties of the studied matrix, the flexural and compressive tests were performed according to the BS EN 1015-11:2019 methods of test and by using a servo-hydraulic testing machine Avery with a load capacity of 600 kN. Properties were obtained with an average of three samples (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Example of mechanical mixing (a), compressive test (b) and (c) flexural tests

Textiles

Three different FRP textiles, composed of glass fibre-reinforced polymer (GFRP), basalt fiber-reinforced polymer (BFRP), and carbon and glass fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP/GFRP), were available to be used in the experimental program (Figure 6). According to the main properties presented by the manufacturers, the CFRP/GFRP and the BFRP textiles were chosen.

Figure 6: FRP textiles

Carbon and glass textile

A bidirectional mesh with high strength, recommended for structural reinforcement of thin-walled structures and that contains carbon (CFRP) and glass (GFRP) fibres in the warp and weft yarns, respectively, was used (Figure 7a). According to the manufacturer, the mesh has 58.5 cords/m, a density of 1.78 g/cm^3 , carbon fibre with a thickness of 0.105 mm, a modulus of elasticity in the warp greater than 240 GPa, a tensile strength of 4300 MPa, maximum strain of 18 %, and a maximum tensile load of 450 kN/m. In this work, the uniaxial tensile tests of one yarn (Figure 7b) were performed according to ASTM D3822/D3822M (2014) by using an EMIC universal testing machine with a load capacity of 600 kN, an external load cell of 50 kN and a Lynx data acquisition system.

Basalt textile

A bidirectional mesh basalt (BFRP) fibre in the warp and weft yarns were also used (Figure 7c). According to the manufacturer, the mesh presents a density of 250 g/cm^2 , a thickness of 0.041 mm, a modulus of elasticity of 74 GPa, a tensile strength of 1980 MPa, a maximum strain of 23 % and %, and a maximum tensile load of 80 kN/m. The mesh has 40 cords/m. Also, the uniaxial tensile tests of one yarn (Figure 7d) were also performed according to ASTM D3822/D3822M (2014).

Figure 7: (a-b) CFRP/CFRP and (c-d) BFRP meshes (dimensions in mm)

Flexural Properties of TRC

The cementitious composite was made using the matrix analyzed in this research and with the use of one, two, or three layers of CFRP/GFRP or BFRP meshes, resulting in specimens with a height of 20 mm, a width of 90 mm and length of 410 mm, as shown in Figure 8.

The composite behaviour evaluation tests were performed according to the ASTM D7264/D7264M (2015) tests, where the specimens were submitted to three-point bending tests with a speed of testing at a rate of crosshead movement of 1.0 mm/min, as shown in Figure 8, also with the use of a servo-hydraulic testing machine Avery with a load capacity of 50 kN. Also, a Linear Variable Differential Transformer (LVDT), with a reading field of 100 mm, was used to measure the mid-span vertical displacement of the specimens.

Considering a beam of homogeneous, elastic material is tested in flexure as a beam simply supported at two outer points and loaded (F) at two central points separated by a distance equal to $1/2$ the support span and at an equal distance from the adjacent support point, the maximum stress at the outer surface occurs between the two central loading points that define the load span (Figure 8).

The stress at the outer surface in the load span region (σ , MPa) may be calculated for any point on the load-deflection curve by using Eq. 1, where L is the support span (mm), b and h are the width and thickness, respectively, in mm. The flexural strength is equal to the maximum stress at the outer surface corresponding to the peak applied force prior to failure.

$$\sigma = \frac{3 \cdot F \cdot L}{4 \cdot b \cdot h^2} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

The maximum strain (ε , in mm/mm) at the outer surface also occurs at mid-span (δ), and it may be calculated according to Eq. 2.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{4,36 \cdot \delta \cdot h}{L^2} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Figure 8: (a) dimensions of the specimens, (b) test arrangement, (c-d) positioning of the meshes and molding of the specimens, and (e) three-point bending test (dimensions in mm).

TRC I-beams

Six 1700 mm long beams with I-sections with 150 mm of flange width, 150 mm of depth, and 20 mm of thickness for both web and flange were cast, one specimen for each condition (Figure 9). The beams were tested in a three-point bending test to assess their flexural performance in three different reinforcement ratios: with one layer (CFRP-GFRP-1 and BFRP-1), two layers (CFRP-GFRP-2 and BFRP-2), and three layers (CFRP-GFRP-3 and BFRP-3) of FRP textiles. The main information on the I-beams can be found in Table 1.

Table 1: Information of the tested beams.

Textile mesh reinforcement material	Textile mesh reinforcement layers	Beams ID	Mass of the reinforcement (g)
Basalt (BFRP)	1	BFRP-1	155.2
	2	BFRP-2	310.3
	3	BFRP-3	465.5
Carbon (CFRP) and Glass (GFRP)	1	CFRP/GFRP-1	177.2 ^(a) 68.5 ^(b)
	2	CFRP/GFRP-2	354.4 ^(a) 137.1 ^(b)
	3	CFRP/GFRP-3	531.6 ^(a) 205.6 ^(b)

(a) CFRP, (b) GFRP

Figure 9: (a) dimensions of I-beams and (b) three-point bending test layout (dimensions in mm).

The I-section beams were cast using a wooden I-shape formwork with the desired final dimensions (Figures 10a-c). The FRP reinforcements were placed in the formwork before the beams were horizontally cast as shown in Figure 10e. It should be noted that spacers were made to help with the positioning of the FRP grids by using the same cementitious material used in the cast.

Also, a nylon line was used along the junction between the web and flanges to keep the layers of the reinforcement together. The I-section beams and the cubic and prismatic specimens were removed from the formwork and moulds after 24 h and kept in a laboratory environment until the test day. On the same dates as the beam testing, the concrete was characterized according to BS EN 1015-11:2019.

Figure 10: (a-c) Wooden I-shape formwork, (b) cross-section dimensions, (d-e) FRP reinforcement, (f) cast of the beams and (g-h) I-beams (dimensions in cm).

The beams were tested in a three-point bending configuration over a 1500 mm span and with a shear span of 750 mm and were supported on the metal profile at a roller and at a fixed support. The loading was applied under 1.0 mm/min displacement control. The load application was measured with an external 50 kN load cell. Mid-span vertical displacements and deformations in the longitudinal reinforcement (SG1 and SG2) and concrete (SG3) were recorded using a data acquisition system. A Linear Variable Differential Transformer (LVDT), with a reading field of 100 mm, was used to measure the mid-span vertical displacement of the beams. Figures 11 and 12 show the instrumentation used in the experimental program.

Figure 11: Instrumentation used in I-beams.

Figure 12: Instrumentation positioned on the reinforced concrete beam.

Results and discussions

Materials and mechanical characterization

Cementitious matrix

The preliminary characterization of the cementitious matrix used in this experimental program was carried out 7, 14, and 28 days after the casting (Table 2) and on the date of the beam tests (Table 3). The flexural (f) and compressive (σ) tests were performed according to BS EN 1015-11:2019. The values in parentheses represent the coefficient of variation (COV) of the specimens. Except for 2-BFRP, all casting presented similar compressive strengths.

Table 2: Results of the flexural and compressive strength tests

7 days		14 days		28 days	
σ (MPa)	f (MPa)	σ (MPa)	f (MPa)	σ (MPa)	f (MPa)
48,8 (3,8)	6,3 (0,2)	51,0 (2,8)	7,6 (0,1)	46,7 (1,5)	7,5 (0,0)

Table 3: Compressive strength

Age	BFRP-1	CFRP-GFRP-1	BFRP-2	CFRP-GFRP-2	BFRP-3	CFRP-GFRP-3
	σ (MPa)					
Beam test	49,9 (8,6)	51,1 (6,7)	25,8 (1,6)	53,7 (3,7)	56,9 (4,4)	45,0 (1,8)

Carbon and glass textile

It is verified that the yarn presented a linear elastic behavior until its rupture, typical of FRPs. The yard presented a maximum average load of 2646.1 (150.7) N. Since the mesh presents 58.5 cords/m, a maximum average load of 154.8 kN can be attained.

Basalt textile

It is verified that the yarn presented a linear elastic behavior until its rupture, typical of FRPs. The yard presented a maximum average load of 881.7 (131.6) N. Since the mesh presents 40 cords/m, a maximum average load of 35.3 kN can be attained.

Flexural Properties of TRC

Table 4 presents the summary of the average results obtained in the flexural tests of the TRC, indicating the maximum load (F_{max}), the flexural strength (σ_{max}), the vertical mid-span displacement ($\delta_{\sigma_{max}}$) and the strains ($\varepsilon_{\sigma_{max}}$) at σ_{max} . The values in parentheses represent the coefficient of variation (COV) of the specimens.

Table 4: Summary of the average results obtained in the flexural composite tests

Specimens	F_{max} (N)	σ_{max} (MPa)	$\delta_{\sigma_{max}}$ (mm)	$\varepsilon_{\sigma_{max}}$ (‰)
WR (unreinforced)	0.3 (0.0)	4.0 (0.6)	0.3 (0.0)	0.3 (0.0)
BFRP – 1 layer	0.7 (0.2)	7.6 (1.4)	0.3 (0.0)	0.3 (0.1)
BFRP – 2 layers	0.8 (0.1)	9.9 (1.4)	0.3 (0.1)	0.4 (0.2)
BFRP – 3 layers	1.0 (0.1)	11.3 (2.0)	4.2 (2.0)	5.6 (2.5)
CFRP/GFRP – 1 layer	2.3 (0.7)	24.7 (6.5)	8.5 (4.1)	11.4 (4.6)
CFRP/GFRP – 2 layers	4.4 (1.3)	61.2 (20.6)	10.0 (0.0)	12.6 (0.1)
CFRP/GFRP – 3 layers	4.4 (0.4)	53.1 (2.6)	8.3 (0.6)	11.3 (0.9)

By analyzing the results presented in Table 4, the presence of the FRP textiles significantly influences the flexural behavior of the tested specimens. It can be noted that the increase of reinforcement area increased the flexural strength of the specimens.

The unreinforced specimens (WR) presented a brittle failure and attained the maximum average flexural strength of 4 MPa, with an average vertical displacement of 0.3mm and an average strain of 0.3‰.

The use of BFRP textiles applied in one, two or three layers provided an average increase in the flexural strength of 90 %, 148 % and 183 % when comparing them to the WR. When analyzing the number of BFRP layers, using two or three layers increased the flexural strength of about 30,3% and 48,7 %, respectively, compared with one layer.

Concerning the CFRP/GFRP grids, using one, two or three layers provided an average increase in the flexural strength of 518 %, 1430 % and 1227 % when compared to the WR. When analyzing the number of CFRP/GFRP layers, using two or three layers increased the flexural strength of about 148% and 115 %, respectively, compared with one layer. Also, an average strain of 11,7 ‰ was attained when using this material.

When comparing the CFRP/GFRP and the BFRP textiles, higher flexural strength values, vertical displacement and strain were attained when using carbon and glass. Using one, two or three layers of CFRP/GFRP provided flexural strengths 225%, 518% and 370% higher than when using BFRP.

So, considering the concrete matrix and the analyzed results, the CFRP/GFRP grid tends to be more effective than the BFRP textiles.

I-beams

To assess the effectiveness of the TRC I-shaped cross-section beams, Figure 13 presents the relationship between the applied load and the vertical displacement at the mid-span. Table 5 presents the summary of the average results obtained in the beams tests for the maximum registered load (F_{max}), the vertical mid-span displacement recorded at that moment (u_{Fmax}), as well as the deformations of the FRP reinforcement (SG1 and SG2) and concrete (SG3) are indicated.

Table 5: Summary of the average results obtained in the TRC I-beams tests

TRC I-beams ID	F_{max} (kN)	u_{Fmax} (mm)	SG1 (‰)	SG2 (‰)	SG3 (‰)
BFRP-1	3.73	1.81	0.18	0.40	-0.13
BFRP-2	6.90	6.79	0.81	3.27	-1.04
BFRP-3	10.88	2.47	m.d.	m.d.	m.d.
CFRP/GFRP-1	9.21	16.13	9.34	8.62	-1.14
CFRP/GFRP-2	11.96	16.72	5.36	5.72	-2.46
CFRP/GFRP-3	35.09	17.05	8.69	4.65	-3.32
m.d. – mechanically damaged					

By analyzing the curves, it is possible to notice that all the beams showed the two stages of the typical behaviour of elements reinforced with FRP materials and submitted to bending. First, the non-cracked concrete stage, with elastic-linear behaviour; the second corresponds to the cracked concrete, with a reduction of the stiffness of the element, and presenting a linear behaviour until a brittle failure.

Regarding the crack opening, the TRC-I beams BFRP-1, BFRP-2 and BFRP-3 (Figure 13a) presented the first crack at the first inflexion points for loads of ~1.6 kN, ~4.4 kN and ~8.2 kN and mid-span displacements of 1.0 mm, 2.0 mm and 0.6 mm, respectively, with a reduction in the stiffness due to the concrete cracking from these points. The BFRP-1, BFRP-2, and BFRP-3 beams presented ~3.7 kN, ~6.9 kN and ~10.9 kN values regarding the maximum average load, indicating an average increase in the load-carrying capacity of 85% and 192% concerning the BFRP-1, respectively. Also, an increase in the average vertical displacement was obtained with the increasing reinforcing layers. Concerning the strains, the maximum values registered at the FRP reinforcement and the concrete substrate were 3.3 ‰ and -1.0 ‰ at the maximum applied load, respectively. Also, no visible concrete crushing was observed for the beams reinforced with basalt.

Concerning the I-beams strengthened with carbon and glass, CFRP/GFRP-1, CFRP/GFRP-2 and CFRP/GFRP-3 (Figure 13b), the crack opening was observed for loads of 2.3 kN, 1.8 kN and 1.6 kN and mid-span displacements of 1.1 mm, 0.7 mm, and 1.2 mm, respectively.

The CFRP/GFRP-1, CFRP/GFRP-2, and CFRP/GFRP-3 presented ~9.2 kN, ~12.0 kN and ~35.0 kN values regarding the maximum average load, indicating an average increase in the load-carrying capacity of 30% and 280% concerning the CFRP/GFRP-1, respectively. The same vertical displacement was obtained with the increase of the reinforcing layers at F_{max} . Concerning the strains, the maximum value registered at the FRP reinforcement was 9.3 ‰, decreasing with the increase of the reinforcing layer. The concrete substrate attained a maximum strain of -3.3 ‰ at the maximum applied load. Likewise, no visible concrete crushing was observed for the beams reinforced with carbon and glass.

Figure 13: Experimental results obtained for the TRC I-beams with BFRF (a) and CFRP/GFRP (b) textiles

When comparing beams that have the same number of textile reinforcement layers (i.e., BFRP-1 vs CFRP/GFRP-1, BFRP-2 vs CFRP/GFRP-2 and BFRP-3 vs CFRP/GFRP-3), the I-beams reinforced with carbon and glass presented higher bending behaviour is observed up to the point of failure. Thus, the beams reinforced with one, two or three layers of carbon/glass attained load-carrying capacities of 146.9 %, 73.3 %, and 230.0 % higher than those with basalt. Thus, better effectiveness was obtained when using the TRC composed with the CFRP/GFRP.

Regarding the failure modes, the tested beams presented three different failure modes: (a) Some of them presented macro-cracks along the moment region until failure, (b) failure governed by shear between support and load application, and (c) premature flange detachment along web-flange junction without mobilization of its maximum due to the weak type of connection used in the experimental program.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, two different types of composites were developed by using bidirectional textiles composed of basalt (BFRP) or carbon/glass (CFRP/GFRP) fibres, and a varying number of reinforcement materials (one to three layers). Later, the composite materials were applied to fabricate textile-reinforced I-beams, and their load-carrying behaviour subjected to bending moments is presented. From the experimental results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The presence of the FRP textiles significantly influences the flexural behaviour of the tested specimens. It can be noted that the increase of reinforcement area increased the flexural strength of the specimens. The unreinforced specimens (WR) presented a brittle failure, while the specimens reinforced with BFRP and CFRP/GFRP textiles BFRP textiles applied in one, two or three layers provided a huge increase in the flexural strength and strains;
- When comparing the CFRP/GFRP and the BFRP textiles, higher flexural strength values, vertical displacement and strain were attained when using carbon and glass. The use of one, two or three layers of CFRP/GFRP provided flexural strengths up to 225%, 518% and 370% higher than when using BFRP;
- Concerning to the TRC I-beams, all elements showed the two stages of the typical behaviour of elements reinforced with FRP materials and submitted to bending. First, the non-cracked concrete stage, with elastic-linear behaviour; the second corresponds to the cracked concrete, with a reduction of the stiffness of the element, and presenting a linear behaviour until a brittle failure, without concrete crushing;
- When comparing elements with the same number of textile reinforcement layers (i.e., BFRP-1 vs CFRP/GFRP-1, BFRP-2 vs CFRP/GFRP-2 and BFRP-3 vs CFRP/GFRP-3), the I-beams reinforced with one, two or three layers of carbon/glass attained load-carrying capacities of 146.9 %, 73.3 %, and 230.0 % higher than the ones with basalt, respectively. Thus, better effectiveness was obtained when using the TRC composed with the CFRP/GFRP.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

CITATIONS

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